

phosphate, tartrate, citrate, ascorbate, sulphate and nitrate, 5 mg each of thiosulphate and thiocyanate, and 3 mg each of EDTA, oxalate, fluoride and bromide were tolerated. Presence of iodide showed high results.

The precision and accuracy of the method were tested by analysing solutions containing a known amount of Rh^{III} following the recommended procedure. The average of six determinations of 97.5 μg Rh was found to be 97.25 μg with the relative mean deviation of $\pm 1.88\%$.

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Analysis of Thallium(III) and Vanadium(IV) in a Mixture

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THE analysis of Tl^{III} and V^{IV} in a mixture is relevant in the context of the intermetallic compound formation between higher oxidation states of vanadium and thallium¹. A redox method for either ion in a mixture is difficult because of

the availability of more than one oxidation state for both. Again, both V^{IV} and Tl^{III} are individually amenable for complexometric estimation by EDTA but the log K values of their complexes are not separated well enough at 18.8 and 21.5 respectively² and thus a complexometric method for the analysis of the mixture is not directly feasible. However, the present method is feasible for the mixture and makes use of the fact that the oxidant Ce^{IV} is active towards oxidation of V^{IV} but comparatively inert towards Tl^{I} .

Experimental

The method of preparation of solutions, stoichiometry of the reaction and other details were as reported earlier³.

The mixture containing V^{IV} and Tl^{III} in the presence of Tl^{I} and V^{V} was subjected to cerimetric estimation of V^{IV} as done earlier⁴⁻⁶. It is followed by a complexometric titration of the resulting solution with EDTA². The results are shown in Table 1. The thallium(III) alone in exactly the same amount as was taken for preparing the mixture, was also taken separately and titrated complexometrically to provide a check of our analysis.

Results and Discussion

The results (Table 1) indicate that 1×10^{-3} – 2.0×10^{-3} mol dm^{-3} of Tl^{III} (2 to 40 mg in 10 ml mixture) can be determined. Analysis of less than 5×10^{-4} mol dm^{-3} of Tl^{III} is not desirable. Similarly, analysis of quantities greater than 2.5×10^{-3} mol dm^{-3} is not feasible due to the formation of a precipitate which obscures the endpoint. The presence of either Tl^{I} or V^{V} , or both, even at the initial stages do not affect the method of analysis. V^{IV} in the range 1.0×10^{-3} – 1.0×10^{-2} mol dm^{-3} in the mixture is feasible. Table 1 also furnishes results of spectrophotometric analysis of V^{IV} for comparison. It is vital that the redox titration is initially done followed by complexometric titration. The procedure is rapid

TABLE 1—ANALYSIS OF OXOVANADIUM(IV) AND THALLIUM(III) IN MIXTURE

Amount present in mixture (mg)				Amount found by titration (mg) and standard deviation				Amount of V^{IV} found by spectrophotometry (mg) and standard deviation	
Tl^{III}	V^{IV}	Tl^{I}	V^{V}	Tl^{III}	S.D.	V^{IV}	S.D.	V^{IV}	S.D.
39.46	24.28	20.19	17.49	39.78	± 0.08	24.06	± 0.10	24.41	± 0.04
27.40	15.54	20.19	11.20	27.12	± 0.10	15.49	± 0.02	15.46	± 0.06
17.54	15.54	20.19	11.20	17.58	± 0.02	15.49	± 0.03	15.46	± 0.03
9.87	34.97	20.19	6.30	9.76	± 0.10	34.60	± 0.08	34.68	± 0.05
4.98	8.74	11.86	6.30	4.94	± 0.04	8.65	± 0.09	8.76	± 0.01
2.47	3.89	5.05	2.80	2.48	± 0.02	3.86	± 0.05	3.83	± 0.03
1.10	8.74	11.86	6.30	1.09	± 0.03	8.70	± 0.06	8.76	± 0.06

and convenient for small quantities of Tl^{III} and V^{IV} in a mixture.

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